

Strain promoted click labeling of oligonucleotides on solid-phase support[☆]

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ABSTRACT

Chemically modified oligonucleotides (ONs) are essential tools in molecular biology, diagnostics, and therapeutics. Strain-promoted azide–alkyne cycloaddition (SPAAC) offers an efficient and bioorthogonal method for ON functionalization. While SPAAC reactions on solid-phase support provide distinct advantages, particularly for the incorporation of lipophilic labels, factors influencing their efficiency remain poorly characterized. The interplay between the physicochemical properties of the modifying molecule, the nature of the solid support, and the labeling site within the ON chain has not been systematically evaluated. In this study, we systematically investigate how modifying molecule properties (size, polarity) and concentration, solid support type, labeling site within the ON chain, and reaction time influence efficiency of labeling. Our findings demonstrate that while polar modifying molecules react efficiently across all solid supports, lipophilic molecules can exhibit reduced reactivity on glass-based supports, particularly in positions close to the 3'-end of the oligonucleotide attached to the support. We further show that conjugation at the 5'-terminus consistently yields the highest efficiencies, with a gradual decline observed as the modification site approaches the 3'-end. A 1 mM concentration of labeling reagent was sufficient to achieve high yields on polystyrene support for all labels and on CPG 500 for the polar labels. The size of the modifying molecule had a lesser effect compared to other factors. The method also benefits from recovery and reusability of the unreacted label. These results enable the rational design of efficient ON labeling protocols on solid-phase support while minimizing reagent consumption, contributing to both cost-effectiveness and environmental sustainability.

1. Introduction

Functionalized synthetic oligonucleotides (ON) [1–3] have attracted considerable attention across the fields of molecular biology, nanotechnology, and biomedical research. ONs play a crucial role in advancements in genetic diagnostics [4,5] and therapeutic strategies, such as antisense and siRNA technologies [6,7]. ON-based platforms are often conjugated with a variety of functional molecules (dyes, carbohydrates, peptides, lipids, etc.) to improve visualization, penetration into cells, or delivery to target tissues [8–11]. In addition to these established uses, ON aptamer–drug conjugates are emerging as promising and more accessible alternatives to antibody–drug conjugates in targeted therapy [12]. Consequently, the development of highly reliable, efficient and economic methods for modifying both synthetic and native ON has become a critical interdisciplinary challenge at the intersection of

molecular biology, chemistry, and physical chemistry.

Synthetic nucleic acids can be chemically modified either during solid-phase synthesis or in post-synthetic steps. Each strategy offers distinct advantages and limitations. Incorporation of modifications during synthesis, typically by using phosphoramidite derivatives of the modifying molecules, is the most straightforward in terms of procedural integration. However, the synthesis of phosphoramidite reagents is often complex and their solutions are prone to degradation, limiting their shelf life and reusability. Moreover, this approach generally requires a large excess of the modifying reagent, most of which cannot be recovered due to the instability of the reactive phosphoramidite moiety.

An alternative strategy involves immobilizing the modifying molecule directly onto the solid support used for oligonucleotide synthesis. While this can simplify the workflow, it restricts the site of modification to the 3'-terminus of the oligonucleotide. Both methods – whether via

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phosphoramidite or support-bound modification – require that the conjugated molecule withstand the harsh conditions of oligonucleotide synthesis, including exposure to strong acids and bases during chain assembly, cleavage from the solid support, and deprotection. Additionally, these approaches are largely confined to laboratories equipped with automated DNA/RNA synthesizers, which are costly and limit access to chemical modification methods for many research groups. This highlights the need for flexible, efficient, and accessible post-synthetic modification strategies.

Post-synthetic labeling offers several advantages over modification during ON synthesis, including reduced consumption of the modifying reagent and protection of the label from the harsh chemical conditions involved in chain assembly. Post-synthetic modification is particularly beneficial for introducing internal modifications, which would otherwise require the label to endure multiple synthetic cycles. This strategy can be implemented either while the ON remains bound to the solid support or in solution after cleavage and deprotection. Each approach presents distinct advantages and limitations. Labeling on solid-phase support requires the conjugated molecule to remain stable under cleavage and deprotection conditions; nevertheless, it offers several notable advantages. Because the oligonucleotide does not need to be dissolved, a wide range of solvents, including lipophilic ones, can be employed, thereby enabling efficient labeling with hydrophobic molecules. In contrast, solution-phase labeling circumvents the requirement for label stability during deprotection, but it is constrained by the generally poor solubility of hydrophobic labels in the predominantly aqueous solvents necessary for dissolving polar oligonucleotides. Reactions on solid support also facilitate purification, as excess reagents can be readily removed by washing. Moreover, the labeling reagent can be recovered and reused, as demonstrated in our study. By comparison, purification of solution-phase products is typically more labor-intensive and does not allow for efficient reagent recovery or recycling.

Several post-synthetic conjugation methods are well-established and widely utilized, including reactions involving active esters [13,14] thiol-thiol or thiol-maleimide couplings [15–17], thiol-reactive acrylic group. However, these methods often suffer from limited efficiency [18–20], particularly when applied on solid supports. Moreover, the potential for recycling unreacted labeling reagents is generally poor; for example, activated esters are susceptible to hydrolysis, while thiol-containing reagents are prone to oxidative degradation. Another option is the use of „click” reactions, among which the strain promoted azide-alkyne cycloaddition (SPAAC) stands out due to its high thermodynamic favorability, biocompatibility, and the absence of a need for any catalysts. However, this method remains underutilized in the context of oligonucleotide conjugation, and its efficiency – particularly under solid-phase conditions – has been only sparsely documented in the literature [21].

SPAAC enables highly efficient and instrumentation-neutral post-synthetic labeling of ON on solid support under conventional laboratory conditions. Initially described by Blomquist and Liu [22] and for biomolecules pioneered by Bertozzi and others [23], it is highly selective and fully biorthogonal [24,25]. It is easy feasible in both water and organic solvents without any susceptibility to air oxidation. Moreover, this method requires no additional reagents except for properly modified ON and molecule to be conjugated. Despite its great potential, the applicability and limitations of SPAAC reaction for conjugation of ONs with organic molecules on the solid support remain insufficiently explored. Majority of published studies to date have focused primarily on reactions conducted in solution [26,27]. Previous studies on post-synthetic click labeling on solid support have predominantly employed CuAAC chemistry [28–34]. Reports utilizing SPAAC in this context are rare and typically limited to terminal modifications using either non-commercial [35] or commercial [36] cyclooctyne building blocks for ON synthesis [37].

In this study, we systematically investigated the key parameters influencing SPAAC efficiency on the solid support. Specifically, we

examined the effects of modifying molecule properties (size, polarity, and concentration), the type of solid support used for oligonucleotide synthesis, and the positional context of the modification within the oligonucleotide chain relative to the solid support. The aim was to identify factors that enhance reaction efficiency and to establish practical, high-yielding conditions suitable for routine labeling in laboratories lacking access to specialized equipment such as automated DNA/RNA synthesizers.

Specific abbreviations used in the text: **ON** – oligonucleotide; **CPG** – controlled pore glass; **PS** – polystyrene; **DBCO** – dibenzoazacyclooctyne; **DBCO-ON** – oligonucleotide modified with dibenzoazacyclooctyne; **AzaPc** – azaphthalocyanine dye; **Cy5** – indocyanine dye Cy5; **BDP** – BODIPY dye; **ACR** – acridine derivative; **AzaPc-ON** – oligonucleotide conjugated with azaphthalocyanine dye; **Cy5-ON** – oligonucleotide conjugated with indocyanine dye Cy5; **BDP-ON** – oligonucleotide conjugated with BODIPY dye; **ACR-ON** – oligonucleotide conjugated with acridine derivative; **L-ON** – oligonucleotide conjugated with one of the conjugated molecules.

2. Experimental

2.1. General

All organic solvents used for synthesis and spectral measurements were of analytical grade (p.a.). Cyanine5 azide (**Cy5**, cat. no. D3030) was purchased from Lumiprobe (Hannover, Germany). The other compounds were prepared according to published methods (**AzaPc** [38], **BDP** [39], **ACR** [40]) (structures shown below). The ONs on solid support were purchased from Generi Biotech (Hradec Kralove, Czech Republic). The MALDI-TOF mass spectra were measured in negative reflectron mode using a MALDI Autoflex II (Bruker Daltonics, Germany) and α -cyano-4-hydroxysuccinic acid as matrix with the addition of HCl. A Druopta pH meter (Prague, Czechoslovakia) was used for buffer preparation. The ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian VNMR S500 (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, USA) spectrometer. The chemical shifts are reported as δ values in ppm and are indirectly referenced to $\text{Si}(\text{CH}_3)_4$ via the residual signal from the solvent. IR spectra were measured on Nicolet 6700 (Thermo Scientific, USA).

2.2. Oligodeoxynucleotide synthesis

ONs were synthesized on Applied Biosystem 392/394 Perkin Elmer DNA/RNA synthesizers in the scale 1 μmol using either FAST protected (for **AzaPc** and **BDP** labeling) or UltraMILD protected nucleoside-phosphoramidite monomers (for **ACR** and **Cy5** labeling) by Generi Biotech s.r.o. (Hradec Kralove, Czech Republic). The synthesis was carried out on polystyrene (columns ABI 3900 HT T Cat. No. 4316674, Thermo Scientific, Applied Biosystems) and on glass supports with defined pore size: CPG 500 Å (DMT-dT-CPG, Cat. No. T301000-1G, Merck, Schnelldorf), CPG 1000 Å (two different suppliers – DMT-dT-CPG, Cat. No. T401000-1G, Merck, Schnelldorf and dT-CPG1000, Cat. No. 20–2031-10, GlenResearch, Sterling, VA, USA) and CPG 2000 Å (two different batches of the same supplier, dT-CPG2000, Cat. No. 20–2032-10, GlenResearch, Sterling, VA, USA). DBCO-modified phosphoramidite building blocks were purchased from Glen Research Inc. (Sterling, VA, USA): 5-DBCO-TEG Phosphoramidite cat. no. 10–1941 for 5'-end of ON and DBCO-dT-CE Phosphoramidite cat. no. 10–1539 for positions 2 and 10 from 3'-end of ON.

2.3. Conjugation and deprotection procedures

The azide derivative of the modifying molecule was dissolved in methanol (for **ACR**) or tetrahydrofuran (for **AzaPc**, **BDP**, and **Cy5**) to concentrations of 0.1 mM, 1 mM, 10 mM, or 100 mM. The click reactions were performed using 30 nmol of oligonucleotide immobilized on the solid support in 1.5 mL glass vials. The appropriate volume of the

modifying molecule solution was added to each vial (200 μL for 1 mM, 10 mM, and 100 mM concentrations; 400 μL for the 0.1 mM solution to maintain stoichiometric excess relative to the oligonucleotide). The reaction mixtures were incubated with gentle shaking at laboratory temperature (21–25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) for 24 h. Upon completion, the modifying molecule solutions were removed by decantation. The solid support was washed three times with the corresponding solvent (methanol or tetrahydrofuran) and dried under atmospheric pressure. The modifying molecule collected from decantation was combined with wash solutions and recovered by solvent evaporation for reuse.

The prepared ONs were cleaved and deprotected at laboratory temperature, either by 32 % ammonia in water (Merck, Schnellendorf, Germany) for 24 h (**AzaPc-ON**, **BDP-ON**) or by UltraMILD deprotection (0.05 M K_2CO_3 in methanol) for 8 h or 2 h for **ACR-ON** and **Cy5-ON** respectively, both at laboratory temperature. The reason for using UltraMILD conditions in the case of labeling with the **ACR** is the instability arising from presence of the aromatic amine linkage, while **Cy5** itself is poorly stable in concentrated ammonia, used as the standard cleavage and deprotection reagent. This choice should not influence the final product, as the remaining two labeling molecules are stable under both types of deprotection conditions. We did not employ UltraMILD conditions for all cases, as we wished to maintain reaction conditions as close as possible to those commonly used. After the cleavage and deprotection, the crude ONs were desalted on hydrated gel filtration columns (CentriPure N10 Zetadex Gel Filtration columns, Emp Biotech GmbH, Berlin, Germany) to remove the low molecular weight impurities. Labeled ONs were then dried under high vacuum (5 mbar) and reconstituted in ultrapure water to a final concentration of 0.5 mM for HPLC analysis. All conjugation experiments were performed in triplicate to ensure reproducibility.

2.4. Chromatographic conditions

Chromatographic analyses and separations were conducted using a Shimadzu LC20 Prominence chromatograph (Kyoto, Japan) consisting of a DGU-20A3 solvent degasser, two LC-20 AD binary gradient pumps, a SIL-20 AC autosampler with a 500 μL sample loop, a CTO-20 AC column oven, an SPD-M20A photodiode array detector (PDA) and a CBM-20 AC communication module. Data acquisition and processing were performed using LabSolution software, version 5.3 (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan).

HPLC gradient grade acetonitrile (ACN) and methanol were purchased from VWR (Prague, Czech Republic). Acetic acid (Ph. Eur. Reagent) was obtained from Merck (Schnellendorf, Germany). Triethylamine was bought from Fluorochem (Dublin, IR). Ultra-pure water was produced using a Millipore purification system (Schwalbach, Germany). 50 mM triethylammonium acetate (TEAA) triethylammonium acetate buffer was prepared freshly from 2 M stock solution adjusted to pH 7 and filtered on nylon membrane 0.22 μm , 47 mm (GVS North America, USA). The column Clarity Oligo-RP™, 3 μm , 4.6 \times 100 mm (Phenomenex, USA) with silica (IV) dioxide core was used. The thermostat was set at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the flow rate of the mobile phase was at 1 mL/min continuously; the injected sample volume was 1 μL . The mobile phase was prepared by mixing ion-pairing solvent (50 mM TEAA) and ACN in a gradient method elution starting from 10 % of organic phase going to 46 % (**ACR-ON**) or 85 % (**AzaPc-ON**, **BDP-ON** and **Cy5-ON**) in 10 min and then continuously eluted for 3 min and 2 min in **ACR-ON** case. All chromatograms were recorded at wavelengths corresponding to the absorption maxima of ON (260 nm) and the individual labels (**Cy5** 650 nm; **AzaPc** 650 nm; **BDP** 500 nm; **ACR** 450 nm).

2.5. Analysis evaluation

In the resulting HPLC chromatograms, the peak areas corresponding to labeled oligonucleotide (L-ON) and DBCO-modified oligonucleotide without the labeling molecule (DBCO-ON) were integrated at 260 nm.

The conjugation efficiency of the reaction was calculated using the ratio of these peak areas according to the following equation (Eq. (1)):

$$\text{yield in \%} = \text{AUC}_{\text{L-ON}} / (\text{AUC}_{\text{DBCO-ON}} + \text{AUC}_{\text{L-ON}}) \times 100$$

where $\text{AUC}_{\text{L-ON}}$ is the peak area of the ON with conjugated molecule (L-ON) and $\text{AUC}_{\text{DBCO-ON}}$ is the peak area of the unreacted DBCO bearing ON (DBCO-ON). Given the design of the study, which was based on comparing the click efficiency of oligonucleotide labeling under different conditions, and since the extinction coefficients of the labeling molecules are very similar, their contribution was not included in the calculation of overall yields. This omission does not significantly affect the validity of the comparative results.

Each independent run of the experiments (as described above) was injected and HPLC analyzed in triplicate resulting in total nine values for each modification position, concentration and label. The average of these values was used to determine the conjugation efficiency. The unmodified oligonucleotide (absorbing only at 260 nm) was also detected by HPLC, typically representing 5–10 % of the product. This fraction reflects the efficiency of the incorporation of the DBCO during the ON synthesis, which was not the focus of this study. Since this oligonucleotide lacks the DBCO moiety required for the reaction, it cannot participate in the conjugation process and was therefore excluded from the calculation of labeling yield by SPAAC.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Design

Mainly two structural types of solid supports are used in commercial syntheses of ON: controlled pore glass (CPG) modified with long-chain alkyl amine spacer and highly cross-linked amino methyl polystyrene (PS). While CPG is of hydrophilic character, the polystyrene is significantly more hydrophobic. CPG is available in a several pore sizes: the CPG 500 \AA is most frequently used for standard commercial ON syntheses, CPG materials with bigger pore sizes (CPG 1000 \AA , 2000 \AA , or more) are recommended for syntheses of long chain ON (typically 50-mers or longer). To explore the influence of character and pore size of the solid support on the labeling efficiency by molecules with various hydrophilicity/hydrophobicity and molecule size, we conducted a comparative study using all commonly employed support types: PS and CPG with pore sizes of 500 \AA , 1000 \AA , and 2000 \AA . The corresponding loadings of these CPG materials were 35–40 $\mu\text{mol/g}$ for 500 \AA , 30 $\mu\text{mol/g}$ for 1000 \AA , and 20 $\mu\text{mol/g}$ for 2000 \AA , respectively.

Dibenzoazacyclooctyne (DBCO) is the only commercially available SPAAC modifier enabling labeling the ON chain in any position except 3'-end using easily synthetically accessible azide bearing labeling molecules. It belongs to the cyclooctynes with the fastest SPAAC kinetic rates ($k = 0.31 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$) [41]. A building blocks incorporating azide into oligonucleotide chain have also been reported [42,43] and at least one is commercially available, but it requires cyclooctyne bearing labeling molecules, which are more difficult to synthesize. In contrast, the use of cyclooctyne in the oligonucleotide chain also allows click reactions with tetrazine [44]. Therefore, for the incorporation of cyclooctyne in the ON chains, we selected two building blocks: DBCO attached directly to the phosphoramidite moiety via aliphatic triethylene glycol spacer for 5'-end labelling (Fig. 1a) and nucleoside-based monomer bearing DBCO on dT phosphoramidite (Fig. 1b) for labeling within the oligonucleotide chain.

The SPAAC enables site-specific modification of ON at 5'-end and/or at any dT chain position, employing commercially available ON modifiers. In case of post-synthetic labeling on solid phase, however, the distance from 3'-end of the ON, which is bound to the solid support, may influence reaction efficiency due to potential steric hindrance and hydrophilic or hydrophobic interactions between the ON and the support. Therefore, to investigate the effect of modification site positioning we selected three labeling sites within a 23-mer oligonucleotide: the 2nd and 10th nucleotides from the 3'-end, and the 5'-terminal nucleotide for

Fig. 1. Phosoramidite building blocks used for synthesis of DBCO-modified ONs. a – DBCO phosphoramidite for attaching at 5-end of ON; b – DBCO dT phosphoramidite for building in any position ON chain.

the click modifications. The position numbering corresponds to the direction of solid-phase ON synthesis (Fig. 2). The sequence chosen for this study, 5'-GTG GAT GAC CAG CTG TTC GTG TT-3', represents ON strand without strongly conformed secondary structures.

A wide variety of functional moieties can be conjugated to synthetic oligonucleotides (ONs) to tailor their properties for specific applications. Commonly employed modifications include fluorescent dyes and quenchers for detection and assay development, affinity tags such as biotin for selective binding and purification, as well as molecules that enhance nucleic acid duplex stability, including minor groove binders, intercalating agents [45–48], modified bases [49], etc. For our study, we selected representatives from these groups, varying in size and lipophilicity. We used a relatively large, highly lipophilic fluorescence quenching azaphthalocyanine molecule **AzaPc** (MW 1596, Fig. 3a), [38] generally less lipophilic commercially available medium size indocyanine fluorophore known as **Cy5** (MW 601, Fig. 3b), smaller BODIPY fluorophore **BDP** (MW 409, Fig. 3c) [39], and more polar intercalating acridine derivative **ACR** (MW 433, Fig. 3d) [40].

During standard ON synthesis using phosphoramidite chemistry, the concentration of building blocks – whether standard nucleosides or non-nucleoside modifiers – typically ranges from 0.07 to 0.1 M. The concentration of labeling reagents for post-synthetic SPAAC labeling of ON in solution varies widely depending on the protocol, ranging from 5 mM to several hundred mM. However, the in-solution methods are not the subject of our study. The studies performing SPAAC solid phase labeling of oligonucleotides still bound on solid support employed concentrations of labeling molecules 133 mM [35] and 270 mM [36]. We used significantly lower concentrations of the selected labeling molecules (0.1 mM, 1 mM, 10 mM, and 100 mM) to evaluate the effect on click reaction efficiency.

In total, conjugations were performed for each combination of solid phase and ON chain modification position using four different modifying molecules, each at four different concentrations. This experimental design yielded a total of 192 combinations (4 solid supports × 3 modification positions × 4 modifiers × 4 modifier concentrations). Each reaction being performed in triplicate to ensure the reproducibility and robustness of the results.

3.2. Click reaction and HPLC analysis

SPAAC reactions of **DBCO-ON** with azide-bearing labels were performed in small-scale volumes (200–400 μ L of solvent) by simply mixing the modified ON on solid-phase support with a solution of the labeling molecules. Reactions were carried out at room temperature without the use of additional catalysts or additives. Following the reaction period (24 h), the solid support was separated from the reaction mixture by centrifugation at 10,000 rpm for 30 s, after which the supernatant containing the labeling dye was carefully removed by pipetting. The solid support was subsequently washed three additional times with the same solvent used for dye dissolution. The wash solutions were combined with the previously collected supernatant and evaporated under reduced pressure, enabling the recovery and reuse of unreacted dye without further purification. After cleavage from the solid support and desalting, the modified ON were analyzed by HPLC.

Three types of ON species were typically present in the analyzed reaction mixtures (Fig. 4). ON labeled by the selected dyes (**L-ON**), unreacted ON modified by DBCO (**DBCO-ON**) and ON lacking **DBCO** modification (**ON**, results of incomplete incorporation of DBCO bearing building block during synthesis of ON chain in DNA/RNA synthesizer). The latter species (unmodified ON) was excluded from click efficiency calculations, as it lacks the reactive DBCO group and therefore cannot participate in SPAAC reactions. The labeled ONs (*i.e.* **AzaPc-ON**, **Cy5-ON**, **BDP-ON** and **ACR-ON**) exhibited absorption spectra characteristic for both the nucleotide backbone and the attached chromophores (Fig. 4d). The modifiers displayed distinct absorption bands with

Fig. 2. Scheme of modified ON positions.

Fig. 3. Structures of molecules selected for conjugations with ONs: a – azaphthalocyanine dye; b – BODIPY dye; c – indocyanine dye Cy5; d – acridine derivative.

Fig. 4. Examples of chromatogram and absorption spectra of labeled ONs. a) Example chromatogram of AzaPc labeled ON (AzaPc-ON), $\lambda = 260$ nm; b) absorption spectrum of unmodified ON; c) absorption spectrum of ON modified with DBCO (DBCO-ON); d) absorption spectra of various L-ONs.

maxima at mid-to-long wavelength regions, in contrast to unmodified ON, which typically exhibit a single maximum around 260 nm (Fig. 4b). DBCO-modified ONs (DBCO-ON), regardless of the modification position, showed an additional bathochromically shifted shoulder near 320 nm in their absorption spectra, attributed to the DBCO moiety (Fig. 4c). Furthermore, each conjugate type was separated by HPLC and further characterized by MALDI-TOF MS to confirm its identity (Figures SI2-

SI13).

In addition to the characteristic absorption spectra the retention times of the unmodified ON sequence and DBCO-ON at all examined positions were determined in separate HPLC runs and served as standards in HPLC runs after labeling.

Based on these standards and typical absorption spectra, we unequivocally identified peaks representing the conjugates (L-ON),

residual starting material (**DBCO-ON**), and unmodified **ON** remaining from incomplete synthesis (Fig. 4a). Example chromatograms of non-conjugated **ON** bearing **DBCO** (Fig. S11A), and **ON** conjugated with **AzaPc** (Fig. S11B), **Cy5** (Fig. S11C), **BDP** (Fig. S11D), and **ACR** (Fig. S11E) in 3 different positions are shown in ESI. For conjugates labeled with **AzaPc**, **BDP**, and **Cy5**, the analytes eluted in the following order: unmodified **ON**, **DBCO-ON**, and **L-ON** (Fig. S11B to S11D). In contrast, the **ACR**-labeled **ON** (**ACR-ON**) exhibited a reversed elution order for the latter two peaks, with the **L-ON** eluting earlier than **DBCO-ON** (Fig. S11E). This shift is attributed to the higher polarity of the **ACR** label compared to the **DBCO** group. For conjugates of smaller molecules, such as **BDP-ON** (Fig. S11D) and **ACR-ON** (Fig. S11E), the labeled product often appeared as a double peak or a single peak with a broadened base. This chromatographic behavior is consistent with previously reported observations in SPAAC reactions and is attributed to the formation of positional isomers during the cycloaddition process, as confirmed by mass spectrometry [40,50]. For this reason, we did not attempt a complete separation of these peaks.

3.3. Analysis of the click reaction

Results from HPLC analysis were compiled and are presented graphically in Fig. 5. These data were subsequently used to evaluate the influence of the investigated parameters on the conjugation yield.

3.3.1. Influence of concentration of conjugated molecules

At the most accessible 5'-end position of the **ON**, a concentration of 0.1 mM was sufficient to achieve quantitative or near-quantitative conjugation yields in SPAAC reactions with **AzaPc**, **Cy5**, and **ACR**. In contrast, effective labeling with **BDP** at this position required a higher concentration of 1 mM. This concentration (1 mM) was subsequently found to be adequate for efficient conjugation under most other labeling conditions and modification positions across all tested labeling molecules.

3.3.2. Influence of the position of the modification in the **ON** chain relative to the solid phase

Labeling efficiency was generally lower at positions proximal to the

solid support, specifically at position 2 from the 3'-end of the oligonucleotide, compared to the more accessible 5'-end. This reduction in efficiency is likely attributable to steric hindrance and reduced conformational flexibility near the point of anchoring, where the **ON** chain is constrained in close proximity to the solid phase.

At the 5'-end, high labeling yields ($\geq 90\%$) were consistently achieved for **AzaPc**, **ACR**, and **Cy5** across all tested solid supports and concentration ranges (0.1–100 mM). In contrast, **BDP** required a minimum concentration of 1 mM to reach comparable yields at this position. Labeling at an internal position—specifically the 10th nucleotide from the 3'-end (position X)—also yielded high efficiencies, ranging from 80% to 100%, independent of the solid support type used.

3.3.3. Influence of lipophilicity/polarity and size of conjugated molecules

The nature of the labeling molecule significantly influenced conjugation efficiency, particularly in relation to the type of solid support used. More polar, ionizable labels such as **Cy5** and **ACR** achieved high labeling yields across all tested modification positions on both controlled pore glass (CPG) and polystyrene (PS) supports. In contrast, the more lipophilic labels, **AzaPc** and **BDP**, exhibited markedly reduced labeling efficiency at positions near the 3'-end and, to a lesser extent, at internal positions when CPG was used as the support.

These findings suggest that lipophilicity, rather than molecular size, is a critical determinant of conjugation efficiency in SPAAC reactions under solid-phase conditions—an effect most pronounced in the case of **BDP**. The decreased efficiency on hydrophilic glass supports may be due to unfavorable interactions between lipophilic dyes and the polar microenvironment near the solid phase.

3.3.4. Influence of the solid phase type

For modifications at the 5'-end of the oligonucleotide, all labeling molecules achieved conjugation efficiencies of 90% or higher across all tested solid supports. Notably, the polystyrene (PS) solid phase consistently afforded high conjugation yields at all modification positions along the oligonucleotide chain. This effect was particularly evident for modifications at the 2nd position from the 3'-end, where PS outperformed all other solid phases. It was the only support that enabled conjugation yields exceeding 90%, with observed efficiencies ranging

Fig. 5. Graphical overview of results. a) Results of conjugations of **ON** with **AzaPc** dye; b) results of conjugations of **ON** with **BODIPY** dye; c) results of conjugations of **ON** with **Cy5** dye; d) results of conjugations of **ON** with **ACR** derivative.

from 94 % to 97 %.

With respect to the CPG supports, as specified in Section 2.2 of the Experimental part, CPG 500 Å was from Merck, but glass supports with higher porosity (CPG 1000 Å) were obtained from two suppliers (Merck and Glen Research). Since Merck does not provide CPG 2000 Å, two independent batches of this material from Glen Research were used to confirm the reproducibility of the unsatisfactory yields on these materials. Overall, glass supports (CPG) yielded lower conjugation efficiencies compared to polystyrene, with the effect becoming more pronounced for CPG materials featuring larger pore sizes (1000 Å and 2000 Å). The greatest disparities were observed for conjugations of **AzaPc** and **BDP** at the 2nd nucleotide position from the 3'-end. In these cases, an increasing trend in yield was noted with rising modifier concentration across all tested CPG pore sizes (500 Å, 1000 Å, and 2000 Å). However, labeling efficiencies at the 2nd position on CPG 1000 Å and 2000 Å were consistently very low or nearly zero for **AzaPc** and **BDP**. These results were reproducible across CPG 1000 Å supports from two different suppliers and multiple batches of CPG 2000 Å from the same source.

For **Cy5** conjugation at the 2nd position on CPG 1000 Å and 2000 Å, labeling efficiencies were higher than those observed for **AzaPc** and **BDP** but did not exceed approximately 80 %, even at the highest **Cy5** concentration tested. In contrast, **ACR** exhibited the best labeling performance on these larger-pore CPG supports, achieving efficiencies up to 60 % at the lowest concentration tested (0.1 mM) and approaching quantitative yields (~100 %) at 10 mM concentration.

3.4. Time necessary for maximal SPAAC labeling

To ensure maximal coupling efficiency, the experiments were performed with a 24-hour reaction time. Subsequently, we examined the minimum reaction time necessary to achieve complete labeling efficiency. From these results, a representative combination of modification position, solid support, and the lowest effective modifier concentration was selected to systematically evaluate the influence of SPAAC reaction duration on conjugation yield.

The minimum reaction time required for complete SPAAC labeling was investigated using oligonucleotides bearing a DBCO modification at the 5'-end, immobilized on 500 Å CPG supports, with a modifier concentration of 1 mM. Reaction times were systematically reduced from 24 h to 12, 6, 1, and 0.5 h, with additional experiments conducted at 10 min (0.17 h). A conjugation time of 30 min was sufficient to achieve maximal labeling yields for **AzaPc** and **BDP**, whereas more polar

modifiers required longer reaction times—1 h for **Cy5** and up to 6 h for **ACR** (Fig. 6). These heterogeneous times further supported the fact that multiple factors closely connected with interaction of solid phase and the labelling molecule apparently influence the kinetic of the reaction. The chemical nature of the labeling molecule is similar (azide is always on aliphatic linker) and that is why the reaction rate is expected to be comparable if the reaction run in solution. Direct determination of the kinetic rate constants is not possible as the reaction run in heterogeneous system with multiple factors affecting the rate as discussed above. However, for comparison the full conversion times of other “click” reactions running in solution in large excess of one of the reactants (i.e., pseudo-first order conditions) are mentioned here. Labeling of the azide-bearing protein by AlexaFluor 488 bearing two different terminal alkynes reached the saturation within the first hour under both Cu-catalyzed and Cu-free (with difluorinated cyclooctyne, DIFO) conditions [51]. Inverse-electron-demand Diels–Alder reaction (IEDDA) of tetrazine-labeled acridines with bicyclo[6.1.0]non-4-yn-9-ylmethanol was finished within 10–60 min [52]. Similar IEDDA of tetrazine-modified naphthalenes with *trans*-cyclooctenol reached plateau phase in 30–60 min [53]. Besides these examples, the reader is recommended the recent review on bioorthogonally activated probes [54].

3.5. Evaluation the recyclability of the labeling dye

The recyclability of the **BDP** labeling dye as a model compound was evaluated over three consecutive SPAAC reactions using a 5'-DBCO-modified oligonucleotide immobilized on CPG 500 Å solid support starting from 10 mM concentration. Comparative nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) and infrared (IR) spectroscopic analyses of the initial and recycled **BDP** samples after each run revealed no detectable structural changes, confirming the chemical stability of the dye throughout the recycling process. HPLC analysis of the labeled oligonucleotides demonstrated consistently high reaction efficiencies across all three cycles, with yields of 92.5 %, 86.0 %, and 90.8 % in the first, second, and third cycles, respectively. Based on these findings, it can be concluded that solid-phase labeling enables several-fold more labeling procedures from the same amount of labeling reagent. Given the high cost of these reagents, this approach significantly reduces expenses and, not least, also minimizes waste, particularly if the method were to be applied for production of larger quantities of labeled oligonucleotides. Detailed experimental procedures and spectral data are provided in the Electronic Supplementary Information (ESI paragraph 4, Figs. S114–S115).

4. Conclusions

Our results demonstrate the high efficiency and broad applicability of the SPAAC methodology for conjugating both polar and lipophilic molecules to oligonucleotides on solid support. To fully leverage this approach, careful consideration must be given to key factors including the choice of oligonucleotide modification site, the concentration of the labeling reagent, and the selection of an appropriate solid support. The impact of these variables varies depending on the physicochemical properties of the labeling molecule and the specific experimental conditions:

1. A key advantage of SPAAC solid-phase support labeling of oligonucleotides is the compatibility with lipophilic, poorly water-soluble modifying molecules dissolved in organic solvents. However, lipophilic labels tend to exhibit reduced reactivity when conjugated on hydrophilic glass solid supports, particularly at modification sites proximal to the solid phase. Under these conditions, the use of polystyrene-based solid supports is recommended—or even necessary—to achieve efficient conjugation.
2. Polar labeling molecules generally exhibit efficient conjugation across all tested solid supports. Nevertheless, polystyrene solid

Fig. 6. Effect of time on SPAAC of all labels on the 5'-end, 500 Å CPG support at 1 mM concentration.

supports tend to provide slightly higher labeling efficiencies, particularly at modification sites located near the solid phase.

- A labeling molecule concentration of 1 mM was sufficient to achieve high conjugation yields under the conditions employed in this study on polystyrene support for all labels and on CPG 500 for the polar labels and is likely applicable more broadly. This relatively low reagent requirement, combined with the potential for near-complete recovery and reuse of unreacted modifiers, offers significant economic and environmental advantages over conventional labeling protocols.
- Conjugation efficiency is highest at the 5'-end of the oligonucleotide chain, with yields gradually decreasing as the modification site approaches the solid-phase-anchored 3'-end at a fixed labeling molecule concentration.
- The size of the modifying molecule appears to have a lesser impact on conjugation efficiency compared to other factors, making this method universal for a wide range of structurally diverse labels.

Considering these findings, the SPAAC method performed on solid support offers significant advantages for oligonucleotide labeling. The data demonstrate the method's high versatility and efficiency, indicating that near-quantitative labeling can be achieved with relatively low concentrations of labeling molecules (~1 mM). This represents a substantial reduction compared to conventional solid-phase oligonucleotide synthesis, which typically employs phosphoramidite building blocks at concentrations around 100 mM. Such lower reagent consumption during SPAAC on solid-phase support is particularly valuable for labeling molecules that are scarce or costly. Furthermore, the SPAAC on solid-phase support protocol requires no additional reagents beyond the solvent, enabling straightforward recovery of unreacted labeling molecules through solvent evaporation. The reactions proceed efficiently under ambient laboratory conditions without the need for heating, thereby reducing energy consumption. We anticipate that these advantages will promote broader adoption of this highly effective, yet underutilized, labeling strategy within the oligonucleotide research community.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: MB and FK performed the experiments during their PhD studies at university. Currently, they are employees of Geneti Biotech that provided the original ON for experiments. There are no other conflicts of interest to declare.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymeth.2025.09.001>.

Data availability

Data for this article, including HPLC records, MS-spectra, evaluation tables are available at Zenodo at [<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14523775>]. The part of data supporting this article have been included as part of the [Supplementary Information](#).

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